

Dynamics of Natural Stands and Response of Seedlings to the Action of Controlled Fire of Three Overexploited Species in the Sudanian Zone (Côte d'Ivoire)

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Abstract

Both natural and anthropic disturbances affect integrity of classified forests in northern Côte d'Ivoire, to point that certain valuable species and their habitats are threatened with extinction. Our work aims to study the structural characteristics and the impact of bush fire regimes on young plants of *Isobertia doka*, *Khaya senegalensis* and *Pterocarpus erinaceus*. from classified forests of Palé and Pouniakélé in north-western Côte d'Ivoire. Data was collected by the surface survey method in 10 plots of one hectare per forest. Dendrometric measurements were carried out in order to determine structural profiles of species studied. An experimental plot made it possible to assess effect of bushfire regimes on the juvenile stage of species. Dendrometric parameters show significant differences with density and mean diameter of the individuals. The densities of individuals ($dbh \geq 5$ cm) of these valuable species are relatively low (0.2-117 individuals / ha), regardless of the forest. In Palé classified forest, three plants species are destructive, synonymous with the instability of their populations. On the other hand, in Pouniakélé forest, *Isobertia doka* have a more stable population than the other two. *Pterocarpus erinaceus* and especially *Khaya senegalensis* are the most vulnerable species in the two plant formations. Late fire has been shown to be the most aggressive on young plants of the species, although the depressive effect can be immediate or delayed depending on whether the seedlings are less than a year old or more than a year old.

Keywords: Structural profiles, dendrometric parameters, fire regime, classified forest, Côte d'Ivoire.

1. INTRODUCTION

In Côte d'Ivoire, wooded areas increased from 15.6 million hectares at the start of the century (Aké-Assi and Dian Boni, 1990) to 3.4 million hectares in 2015 (BNET, 2015). This loss of forest cover is mainly attributable to human activities, because according to Djego *et al.* (2012), the majority of populations live off these natural resources for multiple reasons (food, commercial, socio-cultural, industrial uses, etc.). To cope with this situation, the Ivorian state has erected certain areas of its forest heritage into classified forests. According to Kouamé *et al.* (2010), following the successive downgrading of 116 forests, the country's classified forest network, which was 231 entities at independence, currently consists of 114 entities managed by the Société de Développement des Forêts (SODEFOR). While many classified forests in the forested south have a development plan for their sustainable management, this is not the case for their counterparts in the Sudanian zone. The latter, considered, no doubt, as forests without economic interests (poor in commercial species), have been neglected for a long time by the public authorities. This is the case of the classified forests of Palé and Pouniakélé located in the Bagoué region in Boundiali. According to Djato (2001), the Protected areas, in the north of the country, are degraded profit from cotton and cashew crops because of the currencies they earn. These anthropogenic activities were amplified following the military-political crisis from 2002 to 2010, which subtracted state control several classified forests in this part of the

country. There has been the birth and development of fraudulent exploitation channels for certain species of timber. Among these are *Isobertia doka*, *Khaya Khaya senegalensis* and *Pterocarpus erinaceus*. These three species are exploited for a whole range of non-wood products, such as medicinal plants, raw materials for crafts (tannin, coloring, resin) and fodder for animals (Adjonou *et al.*, 2010; Dourma, 2009). Unfortunately, few studies have focused on these multipurpose species that are on the IUCN Red List of Endangered Species. Thus, it appears important to carry out scientific investigations aimed at making it possible to know the availability and the dynamics of the populations of these useful plants, especially in the classified forests which constitute, a priori, their last refuge. The present study is a contribution to the sustainable management of forest resources. Specifically, it involves evaluating dendrometric parameters, characterizing the structure of populations and evaluating the impact of bush fires, in a controlled environment, on the juvenile stage of these commonly exploited species.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Study site

The classified forest of the Palé, named after the Palé river which takes its source there, is located in the center of the Bagoué region, in the sub-Sudanese sector. It extends between 9 ° 50 'and 9 ° 35' North latitude and between 6 ° 45 'and 4 ° 35' West longitude. The classified forest of Pouniakélé, named after the village located on its southern periphery, is located in the extreme north of the same region, in the Sudanese sector and extends between 6 ° 35 'and 6 ° 25' North latitude and between 10 ° 5 'and 10 ° 20' West longitude (Figure 1). The climate is described as Sudanese type or dry tropical savannah climate with two seasons: a dry season which extends from November to March and a wet season from April to October. Temperatures vary little, ranging from 25 to 31 ° C. The annual average temperature is 26.7 ° C. According to the work of Cort and Kenji (2001), the classified forests of Palé and Pouniakélé are located at the isohyet of 1300 mm of rainfall per year. The hydrographic potential is essentially based on rivers and temporary backwaters which are tributaries of the Bagoué River. The vegetation is that of the sub-Sudanese and Sudanese sectors as described by Kouamé *et al.* (2010). It is essentially about gallery forests, open forests and savannas. The savannas are wooded, shrubby and grassy.

2.2. Study method

For the study of the structure of the species, the sampling plan was designed so as to make an inventory of the forests according to the four cardinal points. The surface survey was used and data collection was carried out in 20 plots of 10,000 m² (1000 x 1000 m), or 10 plots per forest. The work in these plots consisted of counting, measuring the circumferences, the total heights and the heights of the boles of the individuals of *Khaya senegalensis*, *Pterocarpus erinaceus* and *Isobertia doka*. The trunk circumference was measured at breast height of a man (approximately 1.3 m from the ground) for individuals greater than 5 cm dbh. Tree individuals with a circumference less than 15.7 cm (diameter <5 cm), placed in the regeneration class (Sambou, 2004; Ouédraogo, 2006), were also counted in the 1 ha plots.

Regarding the study of the impact of bush fire regimes on young plants, the experimental device consists of a 1 ha plot on which were planted, on the one hand, seedlings of less than 'one year old, produced in the nursery, and on the other hand, seedlings over one year old, obtained under the conditions. The 1 ha plot was subdivided into 3 sub-plots (SP1, SP2 and SP3) of 90 m² (30 m x 30 m), spaced by a firewall of 5 m. SP1 and SP2 underwent early and late fire treatment, respectively. SP3 served as a control (unburned) plot. Each sub-plot was subdivided into 3 blocks corresponding to the three species concerned by the study. The blocks are in turn segmented into 2 plots corresponding, one, to seedlings less than one year old and the other to seedlings over one year old. For each plot, 4 replicates of 25 seedlings were established, for a total of 100 seedlings per sampling unit. In accordance with the work of Aubréville (1953) the fires were set in december (feu early) and in march (late fire).

Figure 1: Location of data collection area

2.3. Analysis methods

2.3.1. Population structure

Dendrometric parameters

The structural parameters retained to characterize the stands of the three species in the two forests studied are density, mean diameter, basal area, biovolume, regeneration index and mean total height. Structural parameters such as density, average diameter and average total height were directly appreciated by arithmetic calculation.

Basal area was calculated according to the following relation:

$$G = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{C^2}{4\pi} \right) \quad (1)$$

Where G denotes the basal area (m²) and C the circumference of the tree (m).

The basal area is the area of the section of the trunks of all trees in a survey at 1.30 m above the ground (Rondeux, 1999). This parameter better reflects the horizontal occupation of the soil by plant species.

Biovolume was calculated by the following formula:

$$V = \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\left(\frac{C^2}{4\pi} \right) \times H \right] \quad (2)$$

Where V denotes the volume of wood (m³) and H the total height of the bole of the tree (m).

Regeneration index is determined by the following formula:

$$Ir = \frac{n_j}{n_a} \quad (3)$$

In this formula, Ir denotes the regeneration index, n_j the total number of young individuals and n_a that of the aged individuals of the species considered. According to Havyarimana (2009), when this index is greater than or equal to 1, the population of the species is balanced, and when it is less than 1, the population of the species is said to be unbalanced.

Distribution of individuals of species

All the individuals with a diameter greater than 5 cm of all the species recorded were distributed by classes of diameter of amplitude 5 cm and by class of height of amplitude 4 cm.

Also, the densities of individuals (in individuals / ha) by diameter classes and by height class were determined.

2.3.2. Effect of bushfire regimes on plants of species

To assess the impact of fires under the different regimes, the number of seedlings, by age category and by species, was determined at two different periods. The first period is before the firing and the second is after the firing. The collection of these data made it possible to calculate the following parameters: the rate of resumption of seedlings before firing, the rate of resumption after firing.

2.4. Statistical data analysis

To compare the calculated parameters, comparison tests of the mean values were carried out thanks to the XLSTAT program. The aim of the analysis is to check whether the means of the values measured in the different groups are significantly different.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Dendrometric parameters of species

The dendrometric parameters of the populations of *I. doka* in the different formations are presented in Table 1. It is noted that the density per foot, the mean diameter and the mean height of the bole show significant differences between the two forests. The highest density (117.4 ± 50.17 vines / ha) was obtained in the classified forest of Pouniakélé., While the largest diameters (29.2 ± 6.66 cm) were observed in the classified forest of the Palé. On the other hand, the basal area, the average height and the biovolume do not present any significant differences. Concerning the dendrometric parameters of the populations of *Pterocarpus erinaceus* (Table 2), it is noted that the density, the mean diameter and the mean total height show significant differences between the two forests. The highest density (16.6 ± 9 , 66 plants / ha) was obtained in the classified forest of Pouniakélé, while the largest diameters (29.78 ± 9.48 cm) come from the classified forest of Palé. No significant difference was observed in basal area and biovolume. For *Khaya senegalensis*, no significant difference was observed in the dendrometric parameters (Table 3). It is particularly noted for this species that the densities in the two forests are less than

Table 1: Mean values of the main dendrometric parameters of *Isobertinia doka* in classified forests

Parameters	Classified forest of Palé	Classified forest of Pouniakélé
Density (stems/ha)	70,2 ± 30,83	117,4 ± 50,17
Average diameter (cm)	29,2 ± 6,66	18,58 ± 5,07
Average total height (m)	13,98 ± 2,93	14,32 ± 8,66
Basal area (m ² /ha)	4,79 ± 1,22	3,58 ± 2,33
Biovolume (m ³ /ha)	26,51 ± 5,24	16,22 ± 12,42

Table 2: Mean values of the main dendrometric parameters of *Pterocarpus erinaceus* in classified forests

Parameters	Classified forest of Palé	Classified forest of Pouniakélé
Density (stems/ha)	7,6 ± 7,49	16,6 ± 9,66
Average diameter (cm)	29,78 ± 9,48	20,95 ± 4,85
Average total height (m)	14,89 ± 3,90	13,84 ± 8,66
Basal area (m ² /ha)	0,45 ± 0,38	0,68 ± 0,51
Biovolume (m ³ /ha)	2,01 ± 1,61	3,14 ± 3,69

Table 3: Mean values of the main dendrometric parameters of *Khaya senegalensis* in classified forests

Parameters	Classified forest of Palé	Classified forest of Pouniakélé
Density (stems/ha)	0,2 ± 0,42	0,5 ± 0,71
Average diameter (cm)	42,51 ± 25,01	34,11 ± 8,33
Average total height (m)	20,63 ± 5,19	19,02 ± 4,61
Basal area (m ² /ha)	0,04 ± 0,11	0,05 ± 0,07
Biovolume (m ³ /ha)	0,08 ± 0,22	0,26 ± 0,46

3.2. Diameter structure of species

Note from Figure 2 that the diameter structure of *Isoberlinia doka* population in the two forests shows different distributions. The distribution in the classified forest of Pouniakélé follows a curve in the shape of an “inverted J” characterized by individuals of small sizes ([20; 25 cm [). For the Palé classified forest, the diameter structure of the *Isoberlinia doka* population presents an asymmetric bell distribution shifted to the right and centered on the diameter class [20; 25 cm [.

For *Pterocarpus erinaceus* populations, the shape of the distribution is similar to asymmetric curves with modal classes of [20; 25 cm [and [10; 15 cm [, respectively, for two forests (Figure 2). There is a low density in the first diameter class.

As for *Khaya senegalensis*, the distribution of the stems presents a bimodal form where the individuals group together only in two diameter classes: the classes [15; 20 cm [and [45; → [and a more regular form in the classified forest of Pouniakélé (Figure 2). In this forest, the shape of the distribution is assimilated to a bell curve with a modal class, the class [35; 40 cm [. We note an absence of individuals in the diameter classes between [5; 20 cm [.

Figure 2: Distribution of individuals of the studied species by diameter classes

3.3. Species height structure

The distribution of individuals of *Isoberlinia doka* from the classified forests of Palé and Pouniakélé, by total height classes (Figure 3) at a bell-shaped, asymmetrical shape, centered on the height class [12; 16 m [. Few individuals have a height greater than or equal to 20 m in the two plant formations.

With regard to *Pterocarpus erinaceus*, the distribution of individuals in the two forests (Figure 3) presents a domed shape, centered on the height classes between 12 and 16 cm. We note an absence of individuals of the class of [2; 4 m [in the two forests and a greater number of individuals with a total height greater than or equal to 20 m, in the Palé forest.

For *Khaya senegalensis*, the population distribution (Figure 3) shows a shape of “J” for the two classified forests. Most trees are 20 m or more in height. We note an absence of individuals with a total height between [2; 8 m [in the two plant formations.

Figure 3: Distribution of individuals of the studied species by total height classes

3.4. Species densities and regeneration indices

The average regeneration density of *Isoberlinia doka* is estimated at 299.70 ± 148.52 plants/ha in the Palé classified forest and 130.7 ± 88.03 plants/ha in the Pouniakélé forest (Table 4). The regeneration index is higher in the Palé classified forest (mean value = 4.89 ± 3.09) than in the Pouniakélé classified forest (mean value = 1.32 ± 1.17).

For *Pterocarpus erinaceus*, the average density of regeneration (Table 4), is estimated at 78.50 ± 69.58 feet/ha in the classified forest of Palé and 88.90 ± 58.27 feet/ha in the classified forest of Pouniakélé.

The average regeneration density of *Khaya senegalensis* (Table 4) is estimated at less than 1 foot/ha in both plant formations (0.50 ± 1.58 feet/ha for the Palé classified forest and 0.80 ± 1.4 feet/ha for the Pouniakélé classified forest). The average values of the regeneration indices obtained are lower than 1. For the Pouniakélé forest, the average value is 0.6 ± 1.07 and for the Palé forest, it is 0.5 ± 1.58 .

Table 4: Densities and regeneration indices of the species studied in classified forests

	Paramètres	Classified forests of Palé	Classified forests of Pouniakélé
<i>Isoberlinia doka</i>	Average density (feet/ha)	$299,70 \pm 148,52$	$130,7 \pm 83,03$
	Regeneration index	$4,89 \pm 3,08$	$1,32 \pm 1,17$
<i>Pterocarpus erinaceus</i>	Average density (feet/ha)	$78,50 \pm 69,58$	$88,9 \pm 58,27$

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	Regeneration index	34,7 ± 50,11	6,12 ± 5,11
<i>Khaya senegalensis</i>	Average density (feet/ha)	0,5 ± 1,58	0,8 ± 1,48
	Regeneration index	0,5 ± 1,58	0,6 ± 1,07

3.5. Impact of bushfire regimes on seedlings of species

The results obtained on the recovery rate of seedlings after planting show that *Khaya senegalensis* is the species with the highest rate ($86.52 \pm 6.67\%$) with seedlings less than 1 year old, while *Pterocarpus erinaceus* records the highest rate ($87.31 \pm 8.83\%$) with seedlings older than 1 year. *Isobertinia doka* has the lowest rates regardless of seedlings category with a lower mean value ($28.53 \pm 12.99\%$) for seedlings older than 1 year (Table 5).

Results on the impact of bushfire regimes on seedlings of the species show that for *Khaya senegalensis*, the highest recovery rate is obtained on the control plot for both categories of seedlings, with average values of 99% (Table 6).

For *Pterocarpus erinaceus*, the control plot gave the best recovery rates of about 99%, while the late fire plot recorded the lowest rates. Seedlings less than one year old had the lowest average value ($55.70 \pm 1.1\%$). For this species, seedlings older than one year had recovery rates above 90% in all three plots (Table 6).

For *Isobertinia doka*, the control plots had the highest recovery rates, with mean values around 99% (Table 6). The late fire plots had the lowest rates, with a lower mean value for seedlings less than one year old ($24.37 \pm 0.6\%$).

The seedlings affected by fire, whatever their age, are taken back from buds located on the main stem and buried in the soil, in *Khaya senegalensis* and *Pterocarpus erinaceus*, on the other hand in *I. doka*, the Recovery of seedlings, whatever their age, is carried out from buds located at the base of the point of contact of the cotyledons and buried in the soil (Figure 8).

Table 5: Recovery rate of seedlings of the species studied before setting fire to the plots

	Seedlings (- 1 an)	Seedlings (+ 1 an)
<i>Khaya senegalensis</i>	86,52 ± 6,67	68,18 ± 8,64
<i>Pterocarpus erinaceus</i>	81,41 ± 10,31	87,31 ± 8,83
<i>Isobertinia doka</i>	77,48 ± 2,67	28,53 ± 12,99

Table 6: Recovery rate of seedlings of the species studied before setting fire to the plots

	Types of seedlings	Telltale	Early fire	Late fire
<i>Khaya senegalensis</i>	-1an	99,25 ± 0,7 ^a	71,42 ± 1,65 ^a	50,63 ± 1,34 ^b
	+ 1 an	99,42 ± 0,83 ^a	62,39 ± 1,44 ^b	60,37 ± 1,94 ^b
<i>Pterocarpus erinaceus</i>	-1an	99,32 ± 0,93 ^a	94,90 ± 2,17 ^b	55,70 ± 1,1 ^c
	+ 1 an	98,74 ± 0,72 ^a	97,54 ± 1,07 ^a	92,75 ± 2,06 ^b
<i>Isobertinia doka</i>	-1an	99,63 ± 0,73 ^a	83,91 ± 1,04 ^b	24,37 ± 0,6 ^c
	+ 1 an	98,38 ± 2,27 ^a	73,68 ± 1,96 ^c	45,22 ± 1,52 ^b

Figure 4: View of the recovery of seedlings affected by fire, of the three species studied.
Tp : Main stem burnt by fire; Ts: Secondary stem from underground bud

4. DISCUSSION

The populations of *Isoberlinia doka*, in the classified forest of Pouniakélé, have a horizontal structure in the shape of an “inverted J”. For species with such a structure, the stems of the future are sufficiently high in number and population renewal is assured (Eyog, 2003 ; Feeley *et al.*, 2007). Such a species is said to be structuring because its perennality in the stands is assured (Biaou, 1999). On the other hand, the species, in this forest, presents a distribution in height in the form of bell. Such a distribution has been observed by Tessi *et al.* (2012), in the relict forests of South Benin and by Kakpo (2011), in the classified forests of Bonou and Ichède of Benin, respectively in *Antiaris toxicaria* and *Dialium guineense*. In the classified forest of Palé, the structures in diameter and in height of the species present a bell shape. The typical bell-shaped structure is due to sporadic regeneration, due to the non-adaptation of species to site conditions (Geldenhuys, 2010). This causes an irregularity in the succession of waves of regeneration.

For *Pterocarpus erinaceus*, individuals show horizontal and vertical bell-shaped structures in both forests. This clearly shows that the current station conditions are not favorable to its abundant and regular generation, nor to its maintenance in forests (Geldenhuys, 2010). Species faithful to this type of distribution in natural forests are said to be destructuring, because they are threatened with extinction in the stands (Sokpon *et al.*, 2002). The predominant individuals are adult individuals in terms of both diameter and height. Similar observations were made by Ouédraogo (2006) in eastern Burkina Faso. The main obstacles are, among others, vegetation fires, pressure from herbivores and reduced rainfall regimes (Bationo *et al.*, 2001; Yameogo, 2005).

With regard to *Khaya senegalensis*, the low density of individuals (less than 1 individual/ha) does not favor a good analysis of structures in diameter and height. This situation testifies to the decline of this species in the plant formations studied, a decline linked to insufficient regeneration and a deficit or even an absence of recruitment. Similar results were observed by Agbangla *et al.* (2015) in forest stands of Niaouli (South Benin) on *Pycnanthus angolensis*.

Considering the natural regeneration of the three species, we note a higher density of plants of *Isoberlinia doka* and *Pterocarpus erinaceus* compared to *Khaya senegalensis* whose regeneration is almost zero. This observation can be explained by the fact that the first two species have developed different vegetative propagation strategies such as rejection, suckering and layering (Adjonou *et al.*, 2010) and *Isoberlinia doka* is the species which presents more dominance of this asexual regeneration (Dourma *et al.*, 2006). In the natural environment, young plants have to cope with drought, bush fires and predators (herbivores), and those that do owe their survival to suckers or their own capacity to develop a tuber (Bellefontaine *et al.*, 2000). The results of the calculation of the regeneration index, show that *Pterocarpus erinaceus* and *Isoberlinia doka* undergo a balanced evolution ($IR \geq 1$), while *Khaya senegalensis* undergo an unbalanced

evolution. According to Havyarimana (2009), a species is considered to have an unbalanced population when its regeneration index is less than 1, while a population is balanced when this index is greater than or equal to 1.

Regarding the impact of fire regimes on the young of the three species, the results showed that, overall, two opposing survival responses were observed depending on the age of the seedlings. For *Pterocarpus erinaceus*, the chances of survival are higher with seedlings older than one year than with seedlings less than one year old. These results corroborate those of Niang-Diop *et al.* (2011) who made the same observation in studying the natural regeneration of *Cordyla pinnata*, in the forest of Fathala, Senegal. According to these authors, individuals resulting from germination of the current year are more affected by abiotic factors (water deficit for example) than older seedlings. But this observation does not seem to be generalizable to all species, because in this study, seedlings less than one year old of *Khaya senegalensis* and *Isoberlinia doka*, gave a high survival rate compared to seedlings older than a year. In nature, many species owe their survival, faced with the influence of abiotic and biotic factors, to cotyledonary buds located in the crown area. We could therefore believe that these buds wilt prematurely and gradually with the age of the seedlings in these two species. We also note that late fire is the one that has the most depressive effect on the two categories of seedlings. This negative effect of late fire is by no means exceptional, insofar as most of the work carried out on the subject (Louppe *et al.*, 1995; Dolidon, 2001) has always shown the clearly depressive effects of late fire. This negative effect can be immediate or delayed depending on the age of the seedling. In *Khaya senegalensis* and *Isoberlinia doka*, the effect of early fire is more marked on seedlings older than one year. This exceptional situation could be explained by the quantity of fuel (total dry biomass) present on each plot, at the time of setting fire (Alvarado, 2012). Insofar as most of the work carried out on the subject (Louppe *et al.*, 1995; Dolidon, 2001) has always shown the clearly depressive effects of late fire. This negative effect can be immediate or delayed depending on the age of the seedling. In *Khaya senegalensis* and *Isoberlinia doka*, the effect of early fire is more marked on seedlings older than one year. This exceptional situation could be explained by the quantity of fuel (total dry biomass) present on each plot, at the time of ignition (Alvarado, 2012). Insofar as most of the work carried out on the subject (Louppe *et al.*, 1995; Dolidon, 2001) has always shown the clearly depressive effects of late fire. This negative effect can be immediate or delayed depending on the age of the seedling. In *Khaya senegalensis* and *Isoberlinia doka*, the effect of early fire is more marked on seedlings older than one year. This exceptional situation could be explained by the quantity of fuel (total dry biomass) present on each plot, at the time of setting fire (Alvarado, 2012).

5. CONCLUSION

Natural formations such as the classified forests of Palé and Pouniakélé, which still constitute forest relics in the northwestern region of Côte d'Ivoire, deserve to be conserved in order to maintain their spatial and temporal structure in a state comparable to the dense humid forests of the South. The study of the population structure of *Isoberlinia doka*, *Khaya Khaya senegalensis* and *Pterocarpus erinaceus* and the resistance capacity of their young plants to fire contributes to a better knowledge of these species in the natural formations of the north of the country. Such a study is a fundamental prerequisite for the development of conservation and sustainable management strategies for classified forests in the sudanian zone. It emerges from this study that the dendrometric parameters of the species commonly exploited are variable from one forest to another. However, in general, the results obtained suggest that the populations of the target species are not very stable overall and will eventually decline if nothing is done to ensure their renewal. *Khaya senegalensis*, which has a very low density and destructive distribution, is by far the most endangered species in these plant formations. The study of the behavior of seedlings subjected to the action of bush fires showed their capacity to regenerate, whatever the type of fire. During the dry season, despite the effect of fire stress, there is a good probability of regeneration survival.

6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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